

How to talk about data documentation – Are we ready to help researchers?

Mari Elisa Kuusniemi
University of Helsinki

Siiri Fuchs
University of Helsinki

Abstract

Researchers are increasingly required to preserve valuable research data they produce. In Finland, the ministry of education has launched a new long-term preservation archive for research data. Therefore, universities are urged to produce support services to help researchers prepare their data for archiving. Help is needed especially for evaluating the value of data and meeting FAIR principles. Here we focus on services needed to improve data documentation.

Communication is the hard part

While piloting a new data preservation service, we helped research groups to create discovery metadata and supplement their data documentation. At first, we bumped into communication difficulties. How to explain even the basic requirement of data documentation, when researchers did not have any education about the topic? How to manage when concepts used by data librarians and researchers are very different? After struggling with the first group, we wrote a guide about data documentation (Kuusniemi & Fuchs 2018). The guide helped us vastly and cut the time needed for consultation to less than half compared to the first pilot.

The benefits of the basic data documentation guide:

- common understanding of data documentation requirements
- common understanding of concepts used

FAIR enough for long-term preservation

When is data structured and documented sufficiently for reuse? The FAIR principles set a goal for reproducible and reusable data. In practice, we need to balance between the principles and the resources available, especially when we try to upgrade the level of

Submitted 5th July 2019

Correspondence should be addressed to Mari Elisa Kuusniemi, Box 53, 00014 University of Helsinki, Finland. Email: mari.elisa.kuusniemi@helsinki.fi

The 15th International Digital Curation Conference takes place on 17-20 February 2020 in Dublin, Ireland

URL: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc20>

Copyright rests with the authors. This work is released under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence. For details please see <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

documentation after the research project. Who can decide when the documentation is FAIR enough? Together with the research groups, we estimated resources needed to improve the documentation for long-term preservation.

Before submission to the new data archive, disciplinary research boards to evaluate the value of the data. To help senior researchers of the boards to evaluate the data from the documentation point of view, we gave them a short report on the data set. In the report, we pointed out the strengths and weaknesses of the documentation, based on the main topics of the documentation guide (Elements of data, page 4).

The report helped the boards:

- to evaluate the data from the reuse point of view
- to understand the main topics of data documentation
- understand the costs of documentation

Need for a new role

After the pilot, we have realised we need a dedicated person to support researchers to accomplish FAIR principles and to help curate and prepare data for preservation. Also, excellent communication skills and understanding about FAIR in research practice are needed.

The new role could include

- consultation service about data documentation
- courses about data documentation
- develop organisational processes and tools around data preservation
- cooperate with data preservation experts of the data archives

In the future, the production of valuable research data should be taken into account when evaluating universities and researchers. This would encourage the development of highly necessary support services.

Reference

Siiri Fuchs, & Mari Elisa Kuusniemi. (2018, December 4). Making a research project understandable - Guide for data documentation (Version 1.2). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1914401>